

Table 2. Selected peptides encoded by circRNAs and miRNAs with oncogenic and oncosuppressor functions.

Peptide sequence names	Peptide length	Cancers	circRNA and miRNA symbols	circRNA and miRNA names	Cellular compartment	Biological unction	Cell lines	References
PINT	87	Glioblastoma	<i>LINC-PINT</i>	long intergenic non-protein coding RNA, p53 induced transcript	cytoplasm	Suppresses cancer cell proliferation	SW1783, Hs683, U251, 293T	[76] 293438 48
SHPRH	146	Glioblastoma	<i>SHPRH</i>	SNF2 histone linker PHD RING helicase	cytoplasm	Suppresses tumour growth	U251, U373	[77]
FBXW7	185	Breast cancer	<i>FBXW7-AS1</i>	FBXW7 antisense RNA 1	cytoplasm	Inhibits cancer cell proliferation and migration	BT549, 4T1	[21]
AXIN1	295	Gastric cancer	<i>AXIN1</i>	axin 1	cytoplasm	Promotes cell proliferation and migration	AGS	[78]
circPPP1R12A	73	Colorectal cancer	<i>PPP1R12A</i>	protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 12A	cytoplasm	Promotes proliferation and metastasis	HT-29, HCT-116, SW480, SW620, LoVo, SW48, DLD-1, Caco2, HCT-15, NCM460	[79]
circMAPK14	175	Colorectal cancer	<i>MAPK14</i>	mitogen-activated protein kinase 14	cytoplasm	Blocks the proliferation and metastasis in cancer cells	SW480, DLD-1, LoVo, HT29, HCT116, Caco2, NCM460	[80]
CORO1C	47	Endometrium tumour	<i>CORO1C</i>	coronin 1C	nucleus	Suppresses cell proliferation and migration	Ishikawa, HEC-1-B	[81]
miPEP133	133	Nasopharyngeal carcinoma, ovarian cancer and cervical cancer	<i>miR-34a</i>	microRNA 34a	mitochondria	Induces apoptosis and inhibits migration and invasion of cancer cells	HNE3, C666-1, CNE2, CNE1, 5-8F, TWO3, NP69	[23]